

Cave Temples of Madurai Pandyas

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Abstract

The thirteenth century was a period of Pandyan revival. The declining of the Chola period facilitated the Pandya to assert their independence. Hinduism was flourished during the period of the second Pandyan Empire. The Pandyas were great patrons of art and architecture. Under the Pandya rulers, the style of architecture flourished and continued. Yanaimalai cavern sanctuary was established during the reign of Jatila Parantaka Nadunjadaiyan, which situated in Madurai District. The Siva Temple is a fine illustration of the early Pandya Rock-Cut Temple architecture. This paper consists of the cave temples of the Pandyas of Arittapatti, Kunnattur, Anaimalai, Tirupparankundram, and Mankulam in Madurai District.

Keywords: Madurai, Pandyan Kings, Cave Temples.

Introduction

The Pandyas contributed a lot to South Indian history and made a culture have some remarkable highlights by building sanctuaries. The Pandya's interest and drive carried some exceptional highlights in social mentalities. The early Pandyas, like the Pallavas, imitated rock-cut and primary sanctuaries utilizing stones. Their procedures motivated the contemporary adjoining rulers, like the Muttraiyars and the Cheras. There are almost 60 cavern temples belittled by the Pandya and the others. The Pandyan landmarks are seen outside the conventional Pandya region. Like the Pallavas and the Pandyas too, they scooped out a solid holy place at Kalugumalai. The early Pandyas utilized rock stones for their underlying temples. The stone-cutting practise of the Pandya began in the seventh century. The nearest cave sanctuary of them all is in Malayadikkurichchi. An engraving of Sendan in it brings up that the cavern sanctuary had a place in the third quarter of the seventh century. During the reign of Jatila Parantaka, most of the Pandya caves were made, like Narasimha Perumal Cave at Anaimalai and Subrahmanya Cave at Tiruparankunram. The Pandya proceeded with the stone-cut practise till the centre of the ninth century, as is obvious from the Sittannavasal cave. The Pandyas were occupied with rock-design customs between the 7th century A.D and the centre of the 9th century.¹ The Pandyas cave temples at Arittapatti, Kunnattur, Anaimalai, Tirupparankundram, and Mankulam in Madurai District are the

subject of this paper. The two stages of Pandyan rock-cut stage are the primary stage is credited to the 7th century A.D and the subsequent stage existed from the mid-9th century A.D. to the tenth century A.D.². The accompanying highlights are the Pandyan Cave Architecture.

Anaimalai Cave Temple

Yanaimalai, which situated in Madurai District and is 10 km from the Mattuthavani bus stand in Madurai. The slope extends more than 3 kilometres (1.9 miles) and is 90 metres (300 ft) high. The word Yanaimalai slope got from the Tamil words *yaanai*, meaning "elephant", and *malai*, meaning "slope". The slope resembles an elephant in a sitting position. The Elephant Hill is a secured landmark and vacation destination in Tamilnadu, India. It has Jain figures, a Shaivite sanctuary, and a Vaishnavite sanctuary, specifically the Narasingam Yoga Narasimha Perumal Temple.³

The Tamil Jain believes Yanaimalai which a holy site of Jain. Jain priests lived here during the Pandyan Dynasty. At the tall edge of this incline, the caves containing of the Jain bas-relief figures of Mahavira, Gomateshwara, and other tirthankaras formed by Jain priests are discovered here. Also stone beds utilised by the priests for resting is here. Two Hindu sanctuaries are at the lower regions of this cave; one being the Ladan cave temple (Ladan Koil), a Shaivite temple devoted to Muruga, and the Yoga Narasimha sanctuary, a Vaishnavite sanctuary committed to Vishnu. Both rock-cut temples are developed by the Pandyas in the eighth century A.D. Where the Ugra Narasimha sanctuary is located and it otherwise called as *Narasingam*. The Tamil-Brahmi and Vattelettu engravings in the sanctuaries show their set of experiences. The Jain sanctuary has been pronounced a sure landmark by the Archeological Survey of India.

The slope is rich in rock and has been harmed by illicit quarrying. In 2010, the public authorities of Tamil Nadu attempted to set up a figure garden on the slope, but retreated after local people and activists challenged the idea. This cavern sanctuary was established at time of Jatila Parantaka Nadunjadaiyan. It was exhumed by Nedunjadaiyan's clergyman Maran Eyinan in Kali era of 3871. It has two engravings – one Sanskrit engraving in Grantha content and one Tamil engraving in Vatteluttu script. The style looks like Mahendravarmā's cavern sanctuaries. In the later of Pandya period, the mandapam and the gopuram were built. Anaimalai was a dwelling place of Jains. To wean individuals from Jainism and include them in the Bhakti Movement, Hindu sanctuaries were uncovered in the spots where Jainism was famous. Additionally, this sanctuary was devoted to Narasimha. The Narasimha and Varaha symbols were considered images of Hindu restoration. This sanctuary was dedicated to Narasimha.

Laden Cave Temple

The cavern is heavily influenced by Tamil Nadu archaeology and is closer to Naarasimha Perumal Cave Temple Narasimham, a modest community which lies 10 km from Madurai District's archaeological element. The essential architect of this cave highlight has a

forward portion, a back divider, stairs, and other building highlights like Ubanam, Jagathi, adjusted Kumdham, Kambu, and the ensuing floor to Brahma Ganga pilasters. The upper part has a Vajanam rooftop with Kapotham. The lower part has an incomplete pathpantha class. Pattigai, kandam, andapatham in the center, pathigai incomplete kumudam, and Jagathi in her, a cavern player, have a front stage floor and fundamental sanctum.⁴

Two holy person models are placed at the Garpagraha's northern and southern side passages. A small holy person form found in the Garudasana act in south. Floor of the Garbagarha fiend, an evil spirit situated at the high speck of the pilasters in Lalithasana, is the stance style of all holy people designed. Bhudaganas have the highlights of giving indications of the primary divinity which called the God couple, Murugan and partner Devi in the ninth century A.D.⁵

Tiruparankunaram Murugan Cave Temple

Tirupparankunram Murugan Temple, located in Tirupparankunram, is a Hindu sanctuary and one of Murugan's six abodes. The temple is of implicit stone-sliced design and is accepted to work by the Pandyas in sixth century A.D. According to legend, Murugan killed the evil spirit Surapadman and wedded Deivayanai, the heavenly little girl of paradise, Indra. He said that to revered Shiva here as Parangirinathar.

The Murugan Cave temple which located 8 kilometres (5.0 mi) from Madurai in Tamilnadu. In this principle sanctuary, aside from Muruga, the gods of Shiva, Vishnu, Vinayaka, and Durga are housed. The sanctuary follows the Shaivite custom of love. Six daily ceremonies and three yearly celebrations held in the sanctuary. The Kantha Sashti celebration is during the Tamil month of Aippasi (October-November) an unmistakable. Thiruparamkundram discovers a notice in Kanda Puranam specifying the killing of Surapadman by Muruga. As per the Hindu legend, Surapadma, an evil ruler who acquired help from Shiva because of extreme retribution, He began administering the 1008 universes because the force achieved. He married Padumakomalai and had a few children. Viramkendiram became his capital, a city built in the oceans, and he began to frighten the Devas. He detained Indra and furthermore, wanted his better half, Indrani. Indra looked for the assistance of Muruga. Muruga sent his courier Viravakutevar to the devil, yet he was unaffected. An extreme fight was battled in Thiruparamkundram, where Muruga killed anyone children of the evil spirit, with except the Iraniyan. Skanda Sashti which celebrated in all Murugan temples in time of Muruga killed Surapadma. Indra, the ruler of the Devas, was intrigued and he wedded Deivayanai, his heavenly little girl, to Muruga at Thiruparamkundram. Muruga is accepted to have adored Shiva here as Parangirinathar. In Kanthar Anoobothi records, Muruga asked anyone heavenly holy messengers and went to the union to fly back to paradise in his vehicles at Manoveham (speed of thought).

Inscriptional confirmations exhibit that the temple, being chop out of a slope, was most likely previously a Jain cavern. There is another hypothesis that prior to this, the Murugan sanctuary existed more pre the sixth century and was changed over into a Jain love

community by Jain priests under the aegis of Pandya lord Koon Pantiyan. The temple was subsequently changed over into a Hindu sanctuary under the tutelage of Gajapathy, the pastor of a later Pandya king, during the latter part of the eighth century. The temple has a few additions from the Madurai Nayak system, which dispatched the sanctuary's pillared lobbies. The Tamilnadu Hindu Religious and Endowment Board maintain and manages the sanctuary today.⁶

The temple is an assembled rock-slice design and tracing go back the Pandya period in the sixth century A.D and the existence models in the mandapas of the Nayaka time frame during the sixteenth century. An Aasthaana Mandapa with a few creatively cut columns leads to the passageway's transcending 150-foot (46 m) high seven-layered rajagopuram. The rock slope behind the temple is 1,050 ft (320 m) and sanctum of Kasi Viswanatha in the high in here. Vinayaka's form in the temple which adorned with sugarcane and fruits. The Kambathadi Mandapam, Ardha Mandapam, and Mahamandapam, the three corridors prompting the sacred place arranged at different heights. The principal hallowed place is an early stone-cut sanctuary which has cells that house the sanctums of Subramanya, Durga, Vinayakar, Shiva, and Vishnu. The managing god Shiva called as *Parangirinathar*, and the female divinity of his partner Parvathi called as Aavudai Nayaki. Boards portraying Shiva's dance of happiness are seen outside the sanctum.⁷

Shiva and Vishnu face each other in the primary holy place is a notable feature of this sanctuary, which uncommon in ancient Hindu sanctuaries. Outside the temple, a tank is as indicated by the sanctuary custom, the fish are presented with salt and rice pieces by the enthusiasts. There is also a Vedic school adjoining the slap of Temple Lake. Before the Dwajasthambam, the banner staff is a cut Nandi, Mayil (peacock), and Mouse (the vehicle of Ganesha). A trip of six stages called the "*Shadashara Padigal*" before Ardha Mandapam is here. The stone carvings of Mahishshasura Mardini, Karpaga Vinayagar, Andarabaranar, and Uggirar are shown in the corridor. Five heavenly water bodies, in particular, Saravana Poigai, Lakshmi Theertham, Saniyasi Kinaru (well), Kasi Sunai, and Sathiya Koopam are here. The temple at Thiruparankuntram is similarly constructed by the Nayak period. The principal sanctum, past the advanced construction, is an early cavern sanctuary. This early cavern sanctuary has regular huge and substantial columns flanked by mortars, with three cells in the principle divider confronting the mandapam, and two side cells confronting one another. Vishnu and the Shivalinga gods are here. In the three different cells are Skanda, Durga, and Ganesa, the mothers needed by two children. The external mass of the cell containing the Shivalinga has two panels portraying the Shiva dance. Early three mortars sort separate the two panels. In one, Shiva is moving, and next, the ensemble keeps time while Parvathy, Nandi, Shivanganas, and other Devas watch the dance and a show-stopper of early Pandya cave figures.

The temple of Tiruparankuntram is a similarly present-day draw of the Nayak period. The garbhagriha is an early cave sanctuary. It has three holy places in the fundamental

divider confronting the mandapa for Durga, Ganesha, and Muruga, and its two side sanctums both god of Siva and Vishnu. In the external mass of garbhagraha portraying the Siva dance, wick to be sure, a show-stopper of early Pandya cave design. The extraneous wall of the Vishnu hallowed place portray the Varaha symbol and Narasimha avatar.⁸ It has further auxiliary sanctums for Gajalakshmi, Bhuvaneshvari, and Jyeshtha. The two sanctuaries for Bhuvaneshvari and Gajalakshmi held at two nearby lower levels next the main garbhagriha to its eastern and western side respectively. The inscriptional proof discusses the temple for Durga and Jyeshtha in the period of Maranjadaiyan by his priest Sattan Ganapathi and his better half, Nakkan. The engravings date from 773 A.D., and the temple style mainstays is similar to that of Mahendravarman I. The south part of Tiruparankunram slope, another cavern temple called the Umaiandavar Kovil, or Thenparankunram Kovil, existed in 8th century A.D. The divider pointing toward the south is Nataraja statue and the garbhagraha pointing toward the east has Arthanareswara sculpture. The sculpture of Muruga with Valli and Deivanai is delightful. Initially, this Jain caverns and later converted to Hindu shrine during the early Pandya period. During Malik Kafur's attack, the sculptures in this cavern sanctuary were somewhat obliterated.⁹

Varichiyur Cave Temple.

Varichiyur cave temple is in a town of Madurai about 15 km east. Hillock which is actually situated at Kunrathur, close to Madurai. The two little caverns disconnect in the hillock, one pointing toward the east named Udayagiri and than pointing toward the west named Asthagiri (from the word Asthamanam). Initially utilised by Jain priests for their safe house during stormy days, it was afterward converted to Shiva's temple by raising Linga in it. The caverns age is traced back to 750 A.D. A little Nandi sculpture could be found before the Linga. Udayagiri cave has one Vinayagar sculpture emblazoned on the divider, which is certainly not a finished one. Dwarabalagar sculptures could be discovered close by it. The most punctual Hindu cavern located at Madya Pradesh in India, which likewise has a similar name, Udayagiri, dated 450 A.D. In Asthagiri's collapse is porch of Garbhagraha, a little space could be found to protect a man or two, which is alluded to as Arthamandapa. It is accepted that a Pandya lord routinely resulted in these present circumstances: Asthagiri cave, doing petition in Arthamandapa, and having the perspective of dusk, which represents the finish of life. In the hillock, we've seen another cavern which additionally has Linga in it, and a nearby place is alluded to as Samanar Padukkai. This load of caverns is inadequate in its structure as it was worked during the conflict time frame between the Pallavas and Pandyas. Segments of following focus are given by Venkataraman:¹⁰

The storm cellar of Linga could be rectangular, octagonal, and roundabout fit. There are 11 implications for Linga, such as image, god, and sexual orientation. Linga may be indicating the Purusha Linga (male), Stri Linga (female), or Purustri Linga (unbiased) depending on his sexual orientation.

Hinduism spins around the ideas of creation, security, and annihilation. Proportionally, Linga is its parts. As the base cellar alludes to Brahma, the centre platform to Vishnu, the top stubha for Shiva and adoring Linga turns into the vital piece of Hinduism. Linga love traced back to 2500 B.C Indus Valley development;

In Hinduism, God see in all types of life and the world. Consequently, the expression "Sarvam Shivamayam" or "Sarvam Vishnumayam" is utilised consistently. Individuals have complete freedom to choose their type of love or practise for Hindu Gods. As a result, agnostic Hindus were also recognised as a group within Hinduism. While Buddhism and Jainism describe life as suffering, Hinduism describes life as happiness (Ananda). The early caverns were worked by Ashoka for Aajeevakas (another gathering of individuals like Buddhism and Jainism), who's way of thinking was that not the one nor other God nor man could help humankind; Also, this gathering was not broadly acknowledged by ensuing lords and it died. Some words have been referenced about this gathering from Tamil legends, Manimegalai and Silappadhikaaram; and Samanar Padukkai, alluded to as' *Kalkanchana* ', signifies' *stone bed*'. The cavern cover considered as' *pali*' by Jains, which transformed into 'Palli' (school) later in Tamil.

Temple of Mangulam Pandamuthu

Mangulam is a twelve-mile drive east of Madurai. The Pandava muttu slope in the cave is to its south, and the upper west part of it is where three little sanctuaries are connected. They are roughly three and a half feet down and seven feet high and look like a stone-cut temple of the traditional kind if they were initially supposed to be connected together to construct a stone-cut temple of the traditional kind. Kalugumalai, a mile east of town, is a stone with some shallow unearthings called Pancha pandava Padukkai, or Pandavas' beds, on the highest point. This place is entirely ringed or converges with water whenever the rain falls in the mountain, and it appears to be a little lake. The mangulam near settlement population groups utilise this water for drinking and washing. This sculpture is over 200 years old, established by the Samanars. This sculpture alludes to the ruler Algar and his wife. This sculpture is behind a shocking tale. This image was taken close to Pannadamuthu lake, and furthermore, that mountain was put close to this lake.

Arittappatti Cave Temple

The Siva Temple is an excellent example of early Pandya Rock-Cut Temple design. This sanctuary, which dates from the seventh and eighth centuries A.D., is a very simple and lovely structure. It has a garbhagriha and a mandapa in the front. Idaichchi mandapam is the name given to this sanctuary by the locals. The temple of Siva This sanctuary's Linga has been carved onto a comparable stone's focal point. Two columns and pilasters flank the front mantapa, which are carved in the early Pandyan style with assistant base and tharanka potikas. Two specialty are cut on the external wall of the sanctuary, one on each side, with bas-relief figures of Vinayaka and Lakulisa Siva separately. The underground sanctuary's architecture and the style of the models help us date the sanctuary to the ninth century A.D.

The Lakulisa mould discovered here is a rare occurrence in Tamilnadu; the companion can be found in Devarmalai, Pudukkottai District, and Porur, Coimbatore. Between these two figures, there exist contrasts. The figure in Arittapatti is wielding the club in his left hand, whereas the figure in Devarmalai is holding it in his right hand. In terms of date, the Devarmalai figure appears to be older than the Arittapatti one. Because of the frequency of this paradigm, we can deduce that the Pasupatha branch of Saivism expanded all the way to the Deep South during the ninth century A.D.¹¹

Arittapatti, a little village outside of Madurai, has a stone-carved Shivan sanctuary dating from the eighth to ninth centuries. Most of the photographs online show far greener fields than I saw on my visit, so this is definitely a piece of rustic life. The region has been dry for the past two years, which isn't ideal for an agrarian town. In the past, they've had a run-in with a stone quarrying company. The town has clearly maintained its space and kumkum. Some antique engravings and Jain carvings can be seen nearby.¹²

In our new review, a demolished Siva sanctuary was found with a later Pandya engraving. This engraving was placed in the 11th year of Jatavarman Vikkiramapandya in 13th century A.D. It records a deal deed of land at a town called Devan Embal by one dealer, Athichcha Devan, nom de plume Siruma Nadalvan, who was an inhabitant of Pathirikkudi under the false name Siruma Nadalvan, who was an occupant of Pathirikkudi under the moniker Ainnurrupperuntheru. Ainnuruvar was a well-known trade group, which spread in south in 8th century A.D. Peruntheru implies a standard market for that specific spot. The old name of Arittapatti is additionally referenced as *Pathirikkudi*. The merchange Athichcha Devan alluded to in this record may be an incredible individual with a Nadalan title. This town, Arittapatti, may have close business contact with nearby focuses as well. The Vellarai Nigama, a trade community alluded to in Mangulam Brahmi's engraving, is found simply 4 km away from Arittapatti. Alagarmalai, where merchants gathered and worked between third and second century B.C., isn't so far from Arittapatti. This load of Jain as well as exchange points which held top the old shipping lane accompanied the Pandya and Chola capitals, Madurai and Uraiur, respectively.¹³

The Pandya Rock-Cut Cave Temples are significant trademark articulation of the creative taste of the kings and the expertise of the craftsmen of their realm. Pandyas temples are likewise the result of a craving to rise above the universe of man-the standards of its narrowing. The styles of its design and development, in addition the customs that occur with its dividers, are completely focused on extreme freedom. The practises and customs of temples exist in history in addition are available, which extraordinarily impacts the socio-social existence of their sib and offers progression to customary. Together, these perspectives reveal the craftsmanship, sculpture, and compositions hidden behind the temple's cutout, which is as relevant today. The cavern sanctuary at Tirupparamkunram, nearly darkened by late reviews, one earlier cavern at Kunnakudi, where a fine Nataraja, covered with plaster work, has lost its initial Pandya highlights. At Tirupparamkunram, the figure Natesa,

conveying the vrishabhadhvaja, reviews a comparable one from Pattadakal, a show-stopper of early Western Chalukyan work, and the impeccable figure of Paravati near Natesa, the Pallava number of sprite in an indistinguishable stance at Mahabalipuram, and its previous sources in a composition from the Vakataka cave at Ajanta and a cutting from the Satavahana rail from Amaravati.

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